

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium(VI) with Pyrogallol and Chlorpromazine Hydrochloride

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Several methods have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium¹. In the course of the investigation on *N*-alkylphenothiazines², it was observed that a reddish yellow mixed ligand complex was formed by uranium(VI) with pyrogallol and chlorpromazine hydrochloride (CPH). The present communication describes a spectrophotometric method for the determination of uranium based on the above observations.

Results and Discussion

Uranium(VI) forms an unstable binary complex with pyrogallol in acetate buffer which exhibits maximum absorbance at 340 nm. However, the addition of CPH converts the binary complex into a ternary complex, which results in bathochromic shift by 40 nm, increased sensitivity and stability of the complex. The complex can be completely extracted into chloroform. Among the various solvents tried chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent as the extractant had higher sensitivity and stability.

The effect of pH on the ternary complex was studied in the pH range 3.5–6.5 using acetate buffer.

The complex exhibited maximum absorbance at pH 5–6. Therefore a buffer solution of pH 5.5 was used.

Maximum absorbance was achieved in the presence of 1–3 ml of 1% pyrogallol and 5–8 ml of 0.4% CPH in chloroform. Hence 2 ml of 1% pyrogallol and 7 ml of 0.4% CPH in chloroform were used. Constant absorbance value was obtained immediately after the extraction and it remained stable for 24 h. The chloroform extract of the ternary complex showed maximum absorbance at 380 nm where the reagent blank absorbed negligibly.

Beer's law was valid over the concentration range 0.8–18 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of uranium. Sandell's sensitivity as calculated from Beer's law data was 0.026 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity of the complex was $0.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The standard deviation and relative error in the determination of 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of uranium(VI) were 0.006 and $\pm 0.8\%$ respectively (ten replicate determinations). The composition of the complex as determined by the equilibrium-shift method³ and slope-ratio method⁴ indicated the formation of 1 : 3 : 1 (uranium : pyrogallol : CPH) complex.

The effect of foreign ions which often accompany uranium was studied with $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of uranium. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance readings was considered tolerable. The tolerance limits of various ions are as follows (figures in the parenthesis represent tolerance limits in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): Mn^{II} (2000); Ni^{II} , Th (500 each); Cr^{III} , Nb^{V} , Ta^{V} (250 each); Ti^{IV} , Re^{VII} , Pt^{IV} (200 each), Co^{II} , La^{III} (100 each); Se^{IV} , Cu^{II} , Rh^{III} , Ir^{III} (50 each), W^{VI} (40); fluoride (50); iodide (500); bromide (1000); phosphate (2000); tartarate, citrate (2500 each); chloride, phosphate, oxalate, nitrate (3000 each); EDTA, ascorbic acid (10000 each). Twenty fold excess of iron(III) and five fold excess of vanadium(V) do not interfere in the presence of 2 ml of 2% ascorbic acid as the masking agent.

Experimental

A stock solution of uranium(VI) was prepared by dissolving uranyl nitrate in distilled water and the solution was made upto 200 ml. It was standardised gravimetrically using 8-hydroxyquinoline⁵. A working solution containing $25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared by diluting the stock solution. A fresh solution of 1% pyrogallol was prepared in alcohol. A 0.4% chlorpromazine hydrochloride was prepared in chloroform. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution was prepared by mixing 0.2 M solutions of sodium acetate and acetic acid. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckman DB spectrophotometer and pH measurements on a L 1-120 digital pH meter.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the stock solution containing upto $180 \mu\text{g}$ of uranium, were added the buffer solution (4 ml), 1% pyrogallol (2 ml) and 0.4% CPH in chloroform (5 ml). The mixture was shaken for 2 min and the layers were

allowed to separate for five min. The chloroform phase was separated and the aqueous phase was again shaken with 0.4% CPH (2 ml). The two chloroform phases were mixed, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and made up to a 10 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 380 nm against a reagent blank.

Uranium in mineral sample: A known quantity of the mineral sample, namely Sy-2 and Sy-3 (0.5 g) was digested with 5 ml of hydrofluoric and sulphuric acids. The residue was dissolved in 3% nitric acid. An aliquot of this solution was evaporated to dryness to remove nitric acid. The residue was dissolved in water and iron(III) in the solution was masked with 2 ml of 2% ascorbic acid and the amount of uranium was determined by following the experimental procedure. The uranium content in the samples were found to be 292 and $655 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively, which were in good agreement with the certified values⁶ of 290 and $650 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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